

The influence of political advertising on social and economic security in Ukraine

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Abstract. The influence of political advertising on social and economic security in Ukraine is investigated in the article. In particular, the research of general characteristics of political advertising as a key factor of social and economic security is carried out. The analysis of advertising expenses of political parties concerning the impact of political advertising expenses on the state budget is carried out and the grouping of political parties on advertising expenses is made. It is shown that political advertising has a negative influence on social and economic security as a result of massive psychological impact on citizens and overload of spending of budgetary funds. The following measures are proposed for increasing of the level of social and economic security of political advertising: adaptation of political advertising technologies to contemporary social attitudes in society; reducing of budgetary expenses on political advertising and attraction more financial resources from commercial entities; using less aggressive methods of psychological influence in political advertising.

Introduction

Political advertising has a significant impact on social and economic security because it determines the characteristics of people's behavior during the election campaign and, accordingly, the trajectory of society's development in the future.

The main purpose of political advertising is changing of political behavior of society or its part within political choices. Political advertising by its principles and functions is a set of specific forms and methods of non-personal representation and promotion of political forces, ideas and practices that contribute both to change of society as a whole and to achievement of individual political goals.

Political advertising is not directed on profit receiving; therefore, it is non-commercial one, along with social and confessional advertising. At the same time, political advertising uses the same means, as commercial one does. They are distinguished only by the purposes. The change in consciousness and behavior of public groups concerning advertising object is the strategic purpose of any political advertising. Political advertising has a considerable potential of impact on mass consciousness thanks to its variety, laconicism and emotionality as well as the commercial one.

Theoretical framework

Political advertising is not regulated specially by the law in a broader sense and submits to the general rules defining associations' and information freedom and an order of use of these freedoms, which are set by laws (Little, 1996). Numerous laws, containing a separate regulation of questions of dissemination of information connected with political activity, operate with a set of terms: political advertising, popularization, promotion. The lack of legislative definition of a concept of political advertising results in ambiguity of its understanding that, in turn, generates conflict situations in legal advertising relationship. There is also no uniform definition of a concept of political advertising in modern scientific

20 November 2020

literature (Nelson, 1974). As a result, inadequate scientific justification generates the low level of legislative fixing of its definition. It, perhaps, is explained by extreme variety of this form of communication and complexity of its regulation at the present stage of development of society and advertising legislation of many countries (Bird & Stevens, 2003).

Political advertizing is directed on change of political behavior of society or its part in political choice conditions. It represents, by its principles and functions, a complex of specific forms and methods of impersonal representation and promotion of the political forces, ideas and practices which specify society change in general and achievement of separate political goals.

Research method

The consolidation as a form of a statistical research is scientific processing of observation data for the further description of statistical set by the generalizing indicators. The essence of statistical consolidation consists in association of units of a set in groups, classes, types.

The grouping as a basic element of statistical consolidation is a distribution of set of the mass phenomena and processes of public life between types and groups by the most characteristic signs. If the indicators are quantitative ones, such type of work is directly called statistical grouping.

The groups, focused on identification of communication between separate characteristics of the studied phenomenon, are called analytical ones.

It is possible to allocate simple and combinational grouping. The grouping, which is carried out by one characteristic, is called simple one. The grouping is called combinational one in case of combination of two and more characteristics.

It is necessary to define the number of groups and intervals of group when making groups.

The simple statistical grouping is a key research method in work. In particular, the grouping of the political parties on advertising expenses is carried out (Granger, 1990).

The size of an interval is defined as a difference between the top and lower borders of an interval. Intervals of group, depending on their size, can be equal and unequal.

In particular, the size of an equal interval is calculated as follows:

$$h = \frac{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}{n},$$

Where x_{\max} , x_{\min} – the maximum and minimum value of indicator in a set;

n – number of groups.

The grouping intervals can be closed and opened (Wilson & Keating, 1994).

The intervals, which have top and lower borders, are called closed ones. In particular, open intervals have only one border: top intervals – the first ones, lower intervals – the last ones.

The object of political advertizing can be presented in the form of a tangible political product (political organization or association, political figure, political project, political action), and also in the form of intangible one (political programs, initiatives, ideas, relations, practices) intended for implementation of certain public changes. Political advertizing is subdivided between the following main groups according to types of advertizing subjects.

1. Political organization advertizing.
2. Political figure advertizing.

20 November 2020

3. Political project advertizing.

This type of advertizing represents the interests and requirements of political forces and is, as a rule, focused not on narrow target group of consumers, but on the audiences united mainly on the social status or on all the society or its considerable part. The political advertizing audiences consist of the political process participants making any choice, supporting any project, initiative or the idea, defining for themselves their political orientation (they make the specific target advertizing group in each case).

The accurate, extremely clear definiteness of political advertising purpose and subject, and also an active, often aggressive nature of its communication influence are the specific features of political advertizing. That is why political advertising is often a threat to the social and economic security. This threat is primarily related to manipulation methods used in political advertising. This influence is based, in the political choice conditions, on the aspiration to convince people to choose only one political product from several possible ones that, as a rule, assumes a various combination of rational and irrational arguments of persuasion which need to have the bigger inspiring force, than arguments of political competitors or opponents. Various methods of influence and substantial filling of advertizing communication serve to this purpose. The use of such influence methods is defined by a concrete situation, intentions and strategy of political force for the benefit of which advertizing activity is carried out. However, quite often the methods and techniques used to achieve the goals of political advertising are unsafe to society because they have a significant impact on public behavior.

The achievement of the separate political advertizing purposes most often consists in motivation of people to carry out the certain actions having political consequences, to participate in these or those political processes, including delegation of various powers by elections. In this sense political advertizing is considered as the special form of communication directed on achievement of the power or public transformations according to the purposes, interests and requirements of these or those political forces. An impact of political advertizing is shown in change of people behavior. However the change of behavior under political advertizing influence is only the resultant act, which is caused by changes of world outlook positions, interests and sympathies in consciousness of people — what defines their behavior and decision-making in the choice conditions. Therefore political advertizing received broad practical application as one of the key components of political technologies of influence on public opinion. The system of the factors forming the political choice is a difficult, multilevel, but rather flexible environment. The political advertizing represents some kind of vector setting the necessary direction of this choice by operating with these factors separately, in a complex or using its different combinations.

The main functions of political advertizing are the following.

1. The communication function. Political advertizing represents one of the specific forms of mass communication or impersonal information exchange. It represents the corresponding communication function, establishing direct and feedback between carriers of the political power or political ideas, applicants for the political power — on the one hand, and society or its part — with another hand. The communication function of political advertizing is the prevailing one regardless of its tasks and political conditions, in which it is carried out, and of existence or lack of the real political choice.

2. The information function. Political advertizing distributes information on political forces, their offers, purposes, intentions and actions. This function promotes the conscious political choice in the conditions of the political competition as helps to compare features of political offers, giving an opportunity to advertizing consumer to make the decision on the choice being informed already. At the same time political advertizing can not only inform the public, but also at the same time can transform information to a certain image which

20 November 2020

becomes some kind of conductor of these or those rational or emotional policies in public consciousness. The features of this image are the following.

1. Simplified nature in comparison with a prototype and extreme availability to mass perception.

2. Demonstration of specificity and uniqueness.

3. Accurate definiteness and concreteness.

4. Mobility and transformation; partial, idealized compliance to a prototype.

3. The ideological function. Political advertizing promotes the distribution of any frame of points of view on reality, at which the public relations are realized and estimated from the point of view of a certain social group. Thereby it influences the consciousness and behavior of audience for the purpose of maintenance or transformation of the social relations according to interests and requirements of carriers of this ideology. The ideological function of political advertizing has mainly focusing and convincing character in the conditions of democracy and political choice. However it can perform the function of ideological promotion with elements of rigid belief at certain stages of development of any state. This function is especially strongly shown at a certain social, political and economic conditions, which characterize the concrete historical period endured by any country in need of society mobilization for the solution of strategic tasks of the state construction, national sovereignty protection, during participation of the state in the external or internal military conflicts, the solution of other global tasks meaning population ideological consolidation.

Nowadays the main customers of political advertizing are the following.

1. Candidate — the person nominated in the order established by the law as an applicant for the position replaced by means of direct elections or for membership in public authority or local government or registered by the relevant election commission as the candidate.

2. Political party — the public association created for participation of citizens in political life of society by means of formation and expression of their political will, participation in public and political actions, in elections and referenda and also for representation of interests of citizens in public authorities and local governments.

3. Public association — the voluntary, self-governed, non-commercial formation created at the initiative of the citizens who united on the basis of community of interests for realization of the common goals specified in the charter of public association.

3. Electoral association — the political party having according to the law the right to participate in elections and also the regional office or other structural division of political party having the right to participate in elections of appropriate level according to the law. Other public association, which charter provides participation in elections and which is created in the form of public organization or social movement and is registered according to the law at the level corresponding to the level of elections or at higher level, is also an electoral association at elections to local governments (Kovalchuk, Khaustova, Demchenko & Volkova, 2018).

4. The Initiative group on holding a referendum — the group of participants of a referendum formed in an order and for term, which are established by the law for realization of an initiative of holding a referendum.

It is worth noting that the higher is the cost of political advertising, the stronger effect it has on society, and the higher is its level of social and economic insecurity. That is why it is necessary to carry out the analysis of expenses on political advertising. As an example the advertising expenses of political parties of Ukraine during 2019 are analyzed.

It is necessary to note that political parties can give advertising under the guise of charity foundation or public organization.

20 November 2020

For example, \$7.49 million were spent on promotion in the third quarter of 2018 by the known political parties (fig. 1).

Most of all the given money was spent by the party “Homeland” – near \$3 million. A considerable part of the given sum, namely \$2.73 million, was spent on political advertizing (fig.2).

Fig. 1. The distribution of expenses on political advertizing in Ukraine between political parties in the third quarter of 2018

Source: Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017, 2018)

The political party “Self-help” is on the second place concerning expenses on promotion. The given party spent \$1.42 million on promotion in the third quarter of 2018. In particular, \$ 0.49 million were the material expenses; \$0.37 million – the popularization activity; \$0.07 million – TV advertizing (fig. 3).

Fig. 2. The distribution of promotion expenses of the political party “Homeland” in the third quarter of 2018

20 November 2020

Source: Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017, 2018)

Fig. 3. The distribution of promotion expenses of the political party “Self-help” in the third quarter of 2018

Source: Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017, 2018)

The political party “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” transferred the most part of money to promotion on local authorities’ level – \$0.75 million (fig. 4). Generally the given party spent \$1.24 million. Despite the visual activity, at the same time the funds on outdoor advertizing placement are not reflected in the report. The political party “Public Front” spent \$0.82 million on salary, rent and taxes.

Fig. 4. The distribution of promotion expenses of the political party “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” in the third quarter of 2018

20 November 2020

Source: Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017, 2018)

The Radical Party of Oleh Lyashko and the party “Opposition Bloc” spent on its promotion only \$0.45. At the same time the majority of the given sum – about \$0.19 million were spent by the Radical Party within popularization activity (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. The distribution of promotion expenses the Radical Party of Oleh Lyashko in the third quarter of 2018

Source: Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017, 2018)

As for the party “Opposition Bloc” – it transferred \$0.34 million to regional representative offices of party.

The overall rating of expenses on promotion of political parties of Ukraine in the third quarter 2018 is presented in tab. 1.

Table 1: The overall rating of expenses on promotion of political parties of Ukraine in the third quarter 2018

The political party	Promotion expenses, \$ million
Homeland	2.73
Self-help	1.42
Petro Poroshenko Bloc	1.24
Popular Front	0.82
The Radical Party of Oleh Lyashko	0.45
Opposition Bloc	0.45
Other parties	0.38
In total	7.49

It is necessary to note that the primary part of expenses on promotion of the above specified political parties consists of funds of the state budget. This is another key factor that determines the impact of political advertising on social and economic security. Thus, in addition to psychological impact on people's behavior, advertising is reflected in the general standard of the population living because it is mainly subsidized by the state budget.

20 November 2020

The grouping of political parties on advertizing expenses

Further it is expedient to carry out grouping of political parties of Ukraine according to the volume of their promotion expenses, in particular, advertizing ones.

The definition of number of groups is carried out mathematically:

$$n = 1 + \frac{3,322}{N} \times N,$$

Where n is a quantity of intervals;

N – Number of units of a set.

According to the data, given in tab. 1, the size of the grouping interval is calculated as follows:

$$h = \frac{2.73 - 0.45}{3} = 0.76.$$

The received grouping looks as follows (tab. 2).

Table 2: The grouping of the political parties by their promotion expenses

Promotion expenses, \$ million	Quantity of political parties	Promotion expenses, \$ million	
		In total	By 1 party
2.73–1.96	3	5.57	1.86
1.96–1.20	-	-	-
1.20–0.44	3	1.72	0.57
In total	6	7.29	-
In average	-	-	1.22

It is possible to see in tab. 2 that expenses of political parties of Ukraine on advertizing are either overestimated, or underestimated.

It is worth noting, based on the distribution received, that political advertising has a negative impact on social and economic security in Ukraine. This is due to the fact that mainly political parties' spending on political advertising is very high - \$5.57 million of the total \$7.29 million is situated in the category with high political advertising costs.

This shows that political advertising has a negative influence on social and economic security as a result of massive psychological impact on citizens and overload of spending of budgetary funds.

Conclusions and proposals for further study

It is highly recommended to upgrade the political advertising to make it more socially and economically secure.

In particular, it is necessary to:

- Adapt political advertising technologies to contemporary social attitudes in society;

20 November 2020

- Reduce budgetary expenses on political advertising and attract more financial resources from commercial entities;
 - Use less aggressive methods of psychological influence in political advertising.
- The proposed complex of actions will significantly increase the level of social and economic security of political advertising in Ukrainian society.

References

1. James B. Bexley and Karen Sherrill (2017). Where to put your money to get their money: a bank advertising awareness study. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 12(1-1), 152-159.
2. Bovee, Courtland L. & Arens, William F. (1989). *Contemporary advertising*. 662 p. Homewood: Irwin.
3. Bovee, Courtland L. & Thill, John V. (1992). *Marketing*. 811 p. New York: McGraw – Hill.
4. Bird, Allan & Stevens, Michael (2003). Toward an emerging global culture and the effects of globalisation on obsolescing national cultures, *Journal of International Management*, 6, pp. 395–407.
5. Brown, R. G. (1963). *Smoothing, Forecasting and Prediction*. 468 p. Cliff, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
6. Burns, Alvin C. & Bush, Ronald F. (2003). *Marketing Research*. 642 p. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
7. Cateora, Philip R. & Graham, John L. (2011). *International Marketing*. 622 p. Irwin: McGraw-Hill.
8. Clark, T. & Mathur, L.L. (2003). Global Myopia: Globalisation Theory in International Business, *Journal of International Management*, 9, pp. 361–372.
9. Czinkota, M., Ronkainen, I. & Zvobgo, G. (2011). *International marketing*. 752 p. Hampshire: Cengage Learning EMEA.
10. Ghauri, P. & Kirpalani Manek, V.H. (2015). *International Entrepreneurship Strategy: Improving SME Performance Globally*. 432 p. London: Edward Elgar Publishing.
11. Ghauri, P.N. & Cateora, P.R. (2010). *International marketing*. 332 p. Irwin: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
12. Ghemawat, Punkaj, (2003). Semiglobalisation and International Business Strategy, *Journal of International business Studies*, 34(1), pp. 139–152.
13. Granger C. W. J. (1990). *Modeling Economic Series*. 419 p. Oxford : Oxford University Press.
14. Harris, G. (1994). International Advertising Standardization: What do the Multinationals Actually Standardize, *Journal of International Marketing*. 2, pp. 13–30.
15. Tareq Hashem (2017). Impact of using humor advertisement on airline customers' mental image. *Innovative Marketing*, 13(3), 25-32. doi:10.21511/im.13(3).2017.03
16. Hollensen, S. (1998). *Global Marketing - Market-Respective Approach*. Hertfordshire, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
17. Kalso, A.M. & Nelson, R.A. (2007). Multinational Corporations and the Challenge of Global Advertising: what do US Headquarters Consider Important in Making Media-selection Decisions, *International Marketing Review*. 24, pp. 563–590.
18. Ko, E. (2007). Cross-national Market Segmentation in the Fashion Industry: a Study of European, Korean, and US Consumers, *International Marketing Review*, 24, pp. 629–651.

20 November 2020

- 19.Kovalchuk, V.G., Khaustova, V. Ye., Demchenko, N. V. & Volkova, M. V. (2018). Global financial system: risks and forecasts, Financial and credit activity: problems of theory and practice, Vol. 1, #24, pp. 368–373.
- 20.Little John D.C. (1996). A Model of Adaptive Control of Promotional Spending. *Operations Research*, 163, pp. 175–197.
- 21.Nelson, P. (1974). Advertising as Information, *Journal of Political Economy*, 82, pp. 729–54.
- 22.Ricks, David A. (2006). *Blunders in International Business*, 192 p. London: Wiley-Blackwell.
- 23.Romin, A.V., Dombrovska, S.M. & Shvedun, V.O. (2018). Aspects of development and implementation of financial strategy of higher educational institution, *Financial and credit activity: problems of theory and practice*, Volume 1, Issue 24, pp. 461–468.
- 24.Root, R.F. (1994). *Entry Strategies for International Markets*. 324 p. San Francisco, California: Jossey-Bass, Inc. Publishers.
- 25.The Internet advertizing share in global expenses will reach 40% in 2018 (2017). <http://mmr.ua/tags/ZenithOptimedia#1556036473.1518525932/> Accessed 13 February 2018.
- 26.The world advertizing market was stabilized (2013). <http://www.advertology.ru/article117805.htm/> Accessed 13 February 2018.
- 27.Streltsov, Volodymyr & Moskalenko, Oleksandr (2015). The European Parliament in the EU-Ukraine relations – from independence to Orange revolution, *Eastern Journal of European Studies*, Volume 6, Issue 2, pp. 111–129.
- 28.Volume of the advertizing and communication market of Ukraine 2016 and forecast of volume of the market of 2017 (2017). <http://sostav.ua/publication/obem-reklamno-kommunikatsionnogo-rynka-ukrainy-2016-i-prognoz-obemov-rynka-2017-73391.html/> Accessed 13 February 2018.
- 29.Wilson, J. H., Keating B. (1994). *Business Forecasting*. 476 p. Irwin: McGraw-Hill Companies.